

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

Transforming ERI and MSI Research Ecosystems: How the Six Conditions of Systems Change Inform Institutional Strategy

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP Consultants Program

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About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution.

The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

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Executive Summary

Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs) represent a broad range of institutions at different stages of research activity and growth with diverse goals, assets, constraints and faculty and student compositions that shape their research priorities and aspirations. Because of this diversity, meaningful improvements to research practice and capacity can be complex and difficult to achieve. Systems change frameworks provide a structured approach for investments and strategies that account for this complexity and nuance. For an ERI seeking to grow its research activity, employing a systems change approach can guide critical investments in research development

(RD), the infrastructure, expertise, and cultural shifts necessary to help advance institutional research goals.

This resource demonstrates how a systems change framework, specifically the six conditions of systems change (*Kania, Kramer, & Senge, 2018*), can be applied to effect institutional change within the research enterprise.

We present case studies of three institutions at different stages of research development, [Hofstra University](#), the [University of San Diego \(USD\)](#), and the [University of Tennessee, Knoxville \(UTK\)](#), exploring how the six conditions help navigate the infrastructure, relationship, and cultural shifts necessary to advance research goals across institutional contexts.

Hofstra was recently (2025) designated a High Research Activity (R2) institution, the University of San Diego (USD) has held R2 status since 2018 and the University of Tennessee, Knoxville (UTK) is a Very High Research Activity (R1) institution.

While all three institutions are working to build research capacity, their differing stages of development shape distinct priorities.

- Hofstra is investing in personnel,
- USD is emphasizing intentional programming to shift research culture and perceptions, and,
- UTK is updating policies to better support increasingly research-active faculty and research-engaged students.

The varied efforts across the institutions are rooted in one or more of the six conditions of systems change: policies, practices, resource flows, relationships and connections, power dynamics, and mental models.

Target Audience

Primary audience: The primary audience is institutional administrators at ERIs seeking to increase research productivity and support and/or sustain growth of research activities at their institution.

These may include **faculty administrators** (e.g., Deans, Associate Provosts) and **staff administrators** in Research Development (RD) and Sponsored Programs (OSP).

Secondary audience: We also Faculty at ERIs engaged in shared governance or other institutional structures that engage faculty in decision-making or policy adoption. Faculty wishing to understand the bureaucratic landscape of systems change related to research and how they may advocate for more RD support at their institution.

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Context and Background

As evidenced by data from the sciences, inequities exist with respect to the distribution of extramural funding across institutions in the U.S. Of 3,733 4-year degree-granting institutions, 131 (or 3.5%) accounted for 75% of academic research and development expenditures in FY21 (National Science Board, 2023). These high-expenditure IHEs are typically Carnegie R1 (Carnegie, 2025) institutions with robust research and sponsored programs (RSP) infrastructures. Minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) are poised to tap into these resources by leveraging systems change frameworks to guide research development (RD) investments. The six conditions of systems change (Kania et al., 2018) offers a change framework to guide decisions about these investments that is applicable across all MSIs and ERIs seeking to expand their RD and RSP enterprises.

The six conditions of systems change (Kania et al., 2018) are those that hold a problem in place (Table 1). They are organized across three levels related to their visibility to individuals and to the level of change they involve. The most visible, tangible, explicit conditions are: policies, practices, and resource flows. Targeting these conditions results in structural change. The other conditions are less visible and tangible, and thereby less explicit. For example, while it is likely that people are aware of relationships and connections and power dynamics within an organization, these are less tangible in that they are not written down in the same way that policies are. Transforming relationships and connections and power dynamics results in relational change. Finally, mental models are implicit; people within an organization may not be aware of them, even as they are influenced by them. Shifting mental models results in transformative change.

While defining and categorizing the conditions provides a framework for discussion, it is critical to understand that the conditions are interdependent, interacting with and influencing each other. It is therefore important to work across all six conditions, being

mindful of how they influence each other in both productive and unproductive ways. For example, a change in policy may be moot if a strong underlying mental model results in stakeholders continuing to follow practices that render the policy ineffective. In contrast, resistance to change at the structural/explicit level can be mitigated by addressing existing norms at the relational/semi-explicit and transformative/implicit levels (Culpepper et al., 2025).

Here we offer case studies from three institutions, exploring each through the lens of the six conditions of systems change.

Each institution is at a different stage of RSP and RD development and has different policies, norms, traditions, stakeholders, and goals, highlighting the broad applicability of the six conditions across institutional contexts.

Six Conditions of Systems Change

TABLE 1

The six conditions of systems change

Condition	Definition (summarized from Kania et al. 2018)	Level of Change
Policies	The rules, regulations and priorities of an institution or organization that guide actions	Structural Change (Explicit)
Practices	The activities, procedures, and informal habits within an institution or organization	Structural Change (Explicit)
Resource Flows	The allocation and distribution of resources within an institution including assets such as money, people, knowledge and information	Structural Change (Explicit)
Relationships & Connections	The connections and communication that occur among individuals within an institution	Relational Change (Semi-Explicit)
Power Dynamics	The distribution of power, authority, and influence (both formal and informal) among individuals	Relational Change (Semi-Explicit)
Mental Models	The underlying culture and habits of thought within an institution; the beliefs, assumptions, and taken-for-granted ways of operating	Transformative Change (Explicit)

The six conditions of systems change interact and influence one another, requiring coordinated structural, relational, and transformative shifts to create lasting change.

Source: Kania et al., 2018

Three Institutions

Hofstra University is a private, non-sectarian, liberal arts institution, founded in 1935. Hofstra enrolls approximately 6,500 undergraduate and 4,000 graduate and professional students in >175 degree programs taught by 1,280 faculty. Hofstra prioritizes teaching and the complementary roles of teaching and scholarly pursuits. Academic programs are housed within 13 schools and colleges including schools of Law, Nursing and Physician Assistant Studies, and Medicine. In 2025, Hofstra earned recognition as an R2 (High Spending and Doctorate Production) institution (Carnegie, 2025) with \$10.43M in research and development spending in FY2024 (Higher Education Research and Development Survey, 2024). Hofstra's goal is to expand its research and sponsored programs capacity in order to grow the number of research-active faculty and research-engaged students while broadening its research and funding portfolio.

University of San Diego (USD) is a private contemporary Catholic university, founded in 1949 enrolling 5,726 undergraduates and 3,384 graduate students in >100 degree programs taught by 1,012 faculty across 7 academic divisions including the College of Arts and Sciences and schools of Business, Engineering, Leadership and Education Sciences, Law, Nursing, and Peace Studies. USD earned R2 Carnegie classification in 2018 and exceeded \$20M in grant revenue in 2024-25. More than 50% of the 2024-25 first-year students belong to minority groups; 30% identified as Hispanic/Latino and 25% are first-generation college students. USD had \$12.6M in R&D spending in FY2024 (Higher Education Research and Development Survey, 2024). USD aims to continue to shift institutional culture to embrace research, and build infrastructure and institutional support to expand activities that contribute to its R2 status.

University of Tennessee Knoxville (UTK) is Tennessee's flagship research institution, offering 63 doctoral programs and 86 master's programs. With over 100 research institutes and centers, UTK generates more than \$350 million in research funding annually. UTK supports research through various specialized labs and consortia: the Office of Research, Innovation & Economic Development oversees research activities, ensuring compliance with ethical standards through the Research Integrity & Assurances office and managing funded projects through the Division of Research Administration. The Office of Faculty Development and Division of Research & Innovation Initiative provide faculty with support in enhancing research and securing external funding. UTK's next goal is to become an AAU institution.

Hofstra University

Problem

Between 2020 and 2024, Hofstra’s R&D expenditures increased more than sevenfold, rising from \$1.45M to \$10.43M (Higher Education Research and Development Survey, 2025). This was driven in part by an increase in federal expenditures, which nearly tripled from \$997K in 2020 to \$2.99M in 2024.

The increase in expenditures facilitated Hofstra’s move to R2 status and offered an opportunity to address capacity gaps between existing research infrastructure and institutional aspirations.

While research, particularly research that engages students, has always been a core tenet at Hofstra, a more concerted focus on research and supporting faculty in obtaining extramural funding necessitated a shift in existing staffing, systems, and processes to accommodate an increase in research and success in securing extramural funding.

Goals and Success Criteria

Hofstra is leveraging its recent R2 designation to expand the research and sponsored programs enterprise with the goal of becoming a “thriving” R2 institution with increasing research and development expenditures. Success will be measured based on changes in expenditures, the proportion of faculty pursuing and receiving external awards, and efficiency in award-related processes.

- **Aim 1.** Center research and pursuit of extramural funding within the institutional culture.
- **Aim 2.** Provide support for submitting proposals and administering awards.
- **Aim 3.** Increase the number of faculty submitting and successfully receiving extramural funds.

Process and Implementation

While addressing all six conditions, Hofstra has focused on relationships and connections as the catalyst for expanding its RSP enterprise. Strategic hiring and stakeholder engagement allowed Hofstra to create new and strengthen existing connections among individuals and units on campus [Relationships and Connections]. It also created opportunities to leverage and shift power dynamics by creating a new Senior Vice Provost for Research and Creative Activities position; moving some post-award responsibilities out of Finance and into the Provost’s Office; and centering and responding to faculty stakeholder voices [Power Dynamics]. Throughout the process, faculty and administrators communicated to develop a shared vision [Mental Models].

The addition of new and shifting of existing roles facilitated a review of Policies, Practices, and Resource Flows to ensure that they address stakeholder needs and align with the shared vision.

HIRING AND PERSONNEL

Faculty

Faculty are the primary drivers of research expenditures as they are the disciplinary experts developing proposals and conducting scholarly and creative activities. As Hofstra expands its RSP enterprise, departments across campus have intentionally hired research-active faculty, cultivating a Mental Model that values research and faculty as teacher-scholars. In many cases, the university has provided larger start-up packages to these new faculty than had historically been offered, a change in Resource Flows. At the same time, some departments modified tenure and promotion guidelines to require application for or receipt of external funding.

This Policy change, supported by the increase in Resource Flows, contributed to a Mental Model that valued research. Importantly, hiring decisions and tenure and promotion guidelines both originate with faculty stakeholders. While administrators ultimately approve hires and guidelines, they do so based on, and in conjunction with, faculty. Thus, faculty-related transformation has been driven by faculty and supported by administrators.

PREVIOUS ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Provost

Vice Provost for Research
and Sponsored Programs

Pre-Award Grants
Manager

Office of
Research and
Sponsored
Programs

Financial Affairs

Grants
Manager

Grants
Accountant

Controller's
Office

CURRENT ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Key Positions Added

Administrators

Administrators are positioned such that they can influence Policies, Practices, and Resource Flows, often by leveraging Relationships and Connections and Power Dynamics. Hofstra hired a new President (2021) and Provost (2022) who brought fresh perspectives to the institution. The Provost was previously a Vice Provost for Research at an R1 institution, contributing experience and an understanding of a research-focused institution. Hofstra subsequently created a new position, Senior Vice Provost for Research and Creative Activities, filled in 2025. This role provides a dedicated senior administrator positioned to work across units (e.g., pre- and post-award, contracts, finance) as a champion for RSP expansion. Listening sessions convened by the new Senior Vice Provost with faculty and other relevant stakeholders (e.g., directors of campus centers and museums) offered a direct line of communication between stakeholders and this new leader.

Hofstra also restructured an existing administrative position. Historically, two pre-award administrators reported to the Provost and two post-award administrators reported to the Vice President of Financial Affairs. Hofstra moved one post-award position into the Provost's Office to build stronger Relationships and Connections between pre- and post-award roles and shift Power Dynamics such that the Provost's Office is more directly involved in decisions regarding post-award policies and processes.

Finally, a new Faculty Fellow role was created in which a grants-active faculty member serves as a conduit between the faculty and the Provost's Office (Relationships & Connections). In this role, the Fellow led focus groups with faculty colleagues across all

disciplines to gather perspectives on Hofstra's transition to R2 status and the supports required to excel in grantsmanship. This created a trusted peer environment in which participants could speak candidly, confident that their feedback would reach senior administrators through an established and reliable conduit.

Engaging Stakeholders

In addition to the Faculty Fellow-led discussions, Hofstra undertook a multi-year [strategic planning process](#) grounded in stakeholder perspectives. In 2021-2022, Hofstra conducted campus-wide focus groups and surveys to allow faculty, administrative, staff, and student stakeholders to identify Hofstra's strengths, challenges, and ambitions. Four priorities emerged from this process: increase support for faculty research, student well-being and success, increase national reputation, and increase community engagement. In 2022-2023, a Strategic Directions Request for Proposals was launched that invited stakeholders to submit ideas for projects aligned with the four priorities. Combined, the stakeholder-identified priorities and projects guided development of a ten year strategic plan. This two-year process shifted historical Power Dynamics by centering stakeholder voices and created a shared vision across campus [Mental Models].

Challenges and Tradeoffs

Communication is a persistent challenge. It can be difficult to ensure that stakeholders are aware of changes given the volume of competing communications across campus. Hofstra has worked to mitigate the communication challenge by engaging as many stakeholders in conversations as possible. The Faculty Fellow role has also supported communication by:

- Positioning a trusted colleague as a conduit between the Provost's Office and the faculty, increasing dialogue across groups;
- Facilitated faculty-led focus groups across disciplines that created space for authentic discussion and translating those insights into actionable guidance for administrators;
- Expanded research development capacity through faculty-led programming

Limited resources impact Hofstra's ability to achieve Research and Sponsored Programs (RSP) goals. A key limiting resource is time. Faculty at Hofstra teach three courses per semester in addition to meeting expectations for scholarship and service. One opportunity under consideration is a reduction in teaching load, possibly through addition of full-time, teaching-focused positions that could assume some instructional

responsibilities currently held by tenure-track faculty, thereby freeing time for research. Implementing this type of change would represent a shift from the existing model, and because Hofstra's faculty is unionized, requires careful consideration and negotiation.

Space is another limited resource on campus with faculty across disciplines facing constraints on available and appropriate space for research and creative activities. The STEM disciplines are experiencing pressure on existing research and laboratory space while colleagues in fine arts face similar pressures with respect to studio spaces. Because new construction is costly and requires long timelines, Hofstra is working to mitigate these challenges by assessing current space utilization and leveraging all available resources, including state infrastructure grants, to provide as much support as possible.

Outcomes and Impact

To date, Hofstra's efforts have focused on building the foundational infrastructure required to support sustainable growth in research and sponsored programs. While comprehensive quantitative outcomes (e.g., changes in proposal volume, awards, or processing times) are not yet available, the institution has implemented a series of targeted structural and policy changes designed to address previously identified barriers. The impacts of these actions are reflected in enhanced capacity, clearer pathways for faculty engagement, and improved alignment between faculty needs and administrative support.

Creation of new and reorganization of existing RSP-related positions directly addressed prior capacity constraints within the research administration ecosystem. This has improved communication across relevant units and created a more seamless research support infrastructure. The Faculty Fellow role responded to challenges related to faculty awareness, trust, and utilization of research support resources. The role has functioned as a trusted intermediary between faculty and research administration, improving the flow of faculty-informed insights into institutional planning while lowering barriers for faculty engagement with RSP services. Engagement of faculty and administrative stakeholders engaged in visioning and strategic planning processes ensured that research expansion efforts were informed by faculty experience and aligned with institutional realities.

Updates to tenure and promotion guidelines more explicitly recognize research and sponsored activity, strengthening alignment between institutional reward structures and expectations for research engagement. Increased start-up funding in selected disciplines enhanced research readiness and supported the recruitment of faculty positioned to pursue externally funded research. In combination with the strategic use of course release, these investments have begun to establish conditions that support engagement with funding opportunities.

Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The following lessons learned and recommendations reflect Hofstra's experience to date in expanding its research and sponsored programs enterprise. Organized by aim, they highlight approaches that supported early progress and may be informative for other institutions at a similar stage of development.

Aim 1. Center research and pursuit of extramural funding within the institutional culture

- + Sustainable institutional change requires intentional alignment of organizational structures and leadership roles. Hofstra's experience suggests that aligning research leadership and reporting structures can improve coordination across research and sponsored programs functions. This alignment can also reinforce the value placed on research, as reflected in hiring practices, tenure and promotion guidelines, and institutional messaging.
- + Trust- and relationship-based mechanisms are essential for centering faculty perspectives on research expectations. Roles such as a Faculty Fellow can serve as effective intermediaries by lowering barriers to communication, strengthening faculty-administrator dialogue, and ensuring that faculty perspectives inform institutional decisions related to research support and expectations.
- + Culture change is more durable when driven through sustained, stakeholder-centered processes rather than one-time or top-down initiatives. Stakeholder-engaged strategic planning can help establish a shared mission around research and support ongoing dialogue to maintain alignment across faculty, administrators, and staff.

Aim 2. Provide support for submitting proposals and administering awards

- + Effective research support depends on coordination across pre- and post-award functions and clear administrative ownership. Hofstra's experience indicates that reorganizing RSP-related roles can improve communication and alignment between pre- and post-award administration.
- + Structural changes to reporting lines can enhance efficiency and responsiveness without adding unnecessary bureaucracy. Elevating research leadership can strengthen oversight of RSP policies and processes and facilitate more cohesive decision-making.

- + Creating approachable, faculty-informed access points is an important consideration for supporting faculty engagement with RSP services. Faculty-facing roles, such as a Faculty Fellow, can reduce barriers to engagement by providing a trusted, low-threshold entry point for faculty seeking research support.

Aim 3. Increase the number of faculty submitting and successfully receiving extramural funds

- + Investments in infrastructure and capacity should precede expectations for measurable increases in proposal submissions and awards. Hofstra's approach highlights the importance of prioritizing foundational investments, such as strategic hiring and role reorganization, to improve research readiness before anticipating growth in proposal volume or funding success.
- + Targeted start-up investments, faculty success programming, and consideration of teaching load can reduce barriers to engagement, particularly for new and early-career faculty developing externally funded research programs.
- + Programming designed and led by experienced faculty peers can strengthen faculty preparedness and confidence in pursuing external funding. Faculty-led focus groups and grant development initiatives can inform institutional decision-making and support sustained growth in proposal activity over time.

University of San Diego

Problem

At USD, The Provost office invested in a new Associate Provost position to focus on research development [Resource Flows, Power Dynamics]. Yet, many of the faculty still did not feel that research was valued on campus as much as it should be. They did not believe they had the time or support to pursue research despite the strong desire to increase their research productivity. They desired time, support and recognition for their scholarship.

Goals and Success Criteria

We aimed to shift the culture at USD to one that valued and championed research rather than one in which research very much took a backseat to teaching [Mental Models] (Fig U1). To build a sense of research support and recognition we sought to develop programs that demonstrated research support [Practices, Policies], celebrated research success, and provided faculty with an avenue for providing feedback and seeking help [Relationships and Connections].

Based on the climate survey we conducted for all faculty across campus, 85% of respondents said they wanted to boost research productivity, and most strongly agreed that research and scholarly activities should be valued at the university (4.6/5). However, when asked if research and scholarly activities are valued at the university, the average answer was lower on the likert scale (3.5/5). To address the disconnect between the administration's desire to boost research productivity and the faculty sentiment that research is not valued as much as it should be at the university, we aimed to:

- + **Aim 1.** Provide more accessible and visible research support resources and personnel and opportunities to seek support.
- + **Aim 2.** Develop workshops and dedicated spaces that support for research
- + **Aim 3.** Provide support and incentives for submitting grant proposals.
- + **Aim 4.** Increase motivation for and celebration of scholarly achievements

Success of these goals are evaluated based on faculty climate surveys that assess awareness and value sentiments, post-event surveys, and percentage increase in grant submissions, and grant dollars awarded.

Process and Implementation

To effectively achieve the described aims, we first conducted a listening tour to assess the needs of the different schools and departments. The Associate Provost met with the Deans of the different schools and visited department Chairs meetings to learn about the different research needs across campus and solicit feedback on potential programs. We rolled out new programs sequentially and mindfully to allow faculty time to realize they exist and try them out, rather than bombarding them with an entire suite of new things that they may struggle to navigate. We also conducted surveys after each event and provided several different methods for providing feedback, to iteratively refine, remove and/or add programming.

Aim 1. Provide more accessible and visible research support resources and personnel and opportunities to seek support. The goal of the initial listening tour was not simply to learn about the needs of the faculty but to increase the visibility of the new Associate Provost role dedicated to supporting and elevating research. We aimed to set a tone that the administration valued research and to provide a face and name of someone faculty could feel comfortable reaching out to for help with research needs. Before this, no one knew who to go to with questions, and when they did reach out to someone they thought could help, they were rarely given what they needed.

As we rolled out new programs, we continued to visit department and school-wide meetings to advertise the new offerings and solicit feedback to raise visibility and awareness.

We created a new **website** dedicated to faculty research support that included an event calendar, funding opportunity database, links to research-related offices, such as Office of Undergraduate Research and Office of Sponsored Programs, research highlight stories on faculty research, a 'comment box' where faculty could provide anonymous feedback or ask questions.

We aimed to set a tone that the administration valued research and to provide a face and name of someone faculty could feel comfortable reaching out to for help with research needs.

We created a new **listserv** that faculty could join to learn about research opportunities, get reminders about upcoming events, etc. Faculty could sign up for the listserv through the website and could register their interests in different topics. The Associate Provost also provided a sign up on the website for **1:1 faculty consultations** where faculty could discuss anything research-related, from brainstorming grant ideas, to asking detailed budget questions, to understanding open access policies and options, to airing grievances.

Aim 2. Develop workshops and dedicated spaces that support research. Major self-identified hurdles that faculty face when seeking grant funding is the time it takes to write proposals, the lack of support in navigating all of the guidelines, the low success rate, and lack of post award support.

To address these issues, we developed **semesterly workshops** on grant proposals and budgets. The grant proposal workshops focused on identifying funding opportunities, understanding the solicitation guidelines, key components of a successful grant proposal, and effective writing tips and strategies. Grant budget workshops focused on understanding the requirements for different types of grants, designing a grant budget, crafting a budget justification, and tracking and managing grant funds after the grant is awarded. These workshops brought together administrators from the Offices of the Provost, Sponsored Programs, and Finance, and to ensure a single cohesive message and provide participants with faces and names of those they can reach out to for support of their scholarly efforts. Workshops were held in-person during lunch hours and lunch was provided. The focus on in-person activities was intentional to foster pre and post workshop conversations and build community.

Faculty also voiced that the lack of time limits their scholarly output such as publications. To encourage scholarly work and provide faculty time and space to write, we also started **Friday Writing Hideaways**, in which we reserved a room in the library for 4 hours every other Friday, provided coffee and donuts, and encouraged

faculty to attend to have a quiet place to write. Writing Hideaways were hugely popular, both for the dedicated time and space where faculty felt they were 'allowed' to work on research, as well as the sense of camaraderie felt among the faculty who attended. Faculty planned to attend with others, providing a natural mechanism for accountability and community; and also formed collaborations and friendships they would otherwise not have.

Aim 3. Provide support and incentives for submitting grant proposals. Beyond the lack of time faculty felt they had to apply for grants, they also were discouraged by the low success rate and the lack of incentives (e.g., rank and tenure, recognition, monetary award). To address these issues, we designed two programs, **PReview** and PREP (Proposal REsubmission Program), to help faculty across all disciplines and units strengthen both first-time and revised proposal submissions. Faculty could apply anytime throughout the calendar year as long as it was 15 weeks prior to the grant submission deadline. To

incentivize participation, faculty who successfully completed either program received a \$500 stipend. PReview aimed to improve the funding success rate of faculty submitting external research grants (~38% institutional average over the last 5 years) by curating an expert review panel to critique the proposal before submission to a funding agency. PReview also included support in the form of consultation meetings, proof-reading, and interfacing with Office of Sponsored Programs (OSP). Faculty who participated in PReview received written reviews on their proposal from 3-5 experts

in their field at least 1 month prior to the proposal submission deadline, and participate in a panel discussion with 3 of the experts who discuss the proposal strengths and weaknesses and give the faculty member an opportunity to ask questions and solicit additional feedback.

Transforming research productivity requires moving beyond providing information to providing partnership. By coupling immersive, in-person workshops with high-touch peer-review programs, we didn't just offer tools—we created an 'accountability community' that reduced barriers, incentivized excellence, and turned declined proposals into successful resubmissions.

PREP aimed to encourage faculty to resubmit proposals that were previously declined by offering strategic support for and strengthening of a revised proposal, including: assessment of initial submission and reviews received from funding agency, expert reviews of the revised proposal, consultation meetings, proof-reading, and interfacing with OSP. PREP in particular was motivated by the fact that the 5-year institutional average success rate of resubmissions was 90%. Yet, of the 62% of proposals that were declined, only 13% of them were resubmitted to the same funding call/program. By not resubmitting declined grants, faculty were missing out on high-success-rate funding opportunities.

To ensure we were able to secure expert reviewers, we offered a modest honorarium of \$250 for the review. We also provided reviewers with forms with specific prompts set by the funding call review criteria to facilitate meaningful reviews. Another important aspect of the program was weekly check-ins and draft feedback before sending to review. This high touch, high-impact program was minimal in cost (~\$1500 per proposal) compared to the grant funding that came from the program and was much cheaper than the fees charged by large grant review companies (e.g., Hanover, KB science).

Aim 4. Increase motivation for and celebration of scholarly achievements. Faculty expressed frustration in their rate of publication. They wanted to publish more papers but they struggled to find the time to get them ready to submit without hard deadlines. Moreover, there was no recognition of their efforts until the paper was published, which is typically months to years after submission, and even then the recognition was minimal at best. To combat these disincentivization structures, we started a program, Celebrating Scholarly Submissions, that recognized faculty who submitted publications or other scholarly works by a specific deadline, with 4 deadlines spaced throughout the year. Faculty who submitted papers by the deadline, completed a form with the paper details and then they were featured on the new research website (Aim 1). We also invited all recognized faculty to a reception and they were entered into a raffle for a gift card. One faculty member each cycle was chosen to be the subject of a feature story on the website, giving them the space to discuss their paper and their research. We strived to feature faculty across all schools and disciplines to show the breadth of research being conducted at the university. The deadlines provided motivation for faculty to submit papers within a certain time frame, and being recognized was further incentive and served to boost the culture of celebration of research and scholarship.

Challenges and Tradeoffs

Aim 1. The primary challenges that arose with Aim 1 were raising awareness of research support services and making sure that all stakeholders felt heard and supported. Despite the listening tour and holding two faculty open forums focused on the needs

of humanities and arts faculty, there remained a view among many that the research support was primarily geared towards STEM. The faculty that engaged in the forums and workshops did not hold this view but reaching and shifting the perception of those that did not engage continued to be an issue. This is in part because shifting culture and perception is a long-game - it takes years - so longitudinal surveys and assessment is critical. We opted for in-person, small group and 1:1 interactions for culture shifting and allowed the website and listserv to be the broad face of increased support. This approach is very high impact for those that engage but requires some word of mouth and patience for a groundswell culture shift - but the shift will be more dramatic and sustainable [relationships and connections].

Aim 2. We faced a similar issue of lack of awareness with the workshops and writing hideaways. Our baseline survey showed that after a year of offering these services, most faculty were unaware of them. Additionally, there is always a time issue, faculty want to attend but have other commitments. We considered hosting virtual events and spending more time developing electronic resources that could be reviewed asynchronously, but we felt that while it may be more accessible to a broader audience the impact for each individual would be significantly lower. This is based on anecdotal evidence and similar shifting of approach in the Office of Undergraduate Research. Shifting from virtual to in-person events and providing more spaces and times to engage with the office personnel led to slightly lower overall attendance of workshops but increased the students engaging in undergraduate research by 5-fold.

Aim 3. The primary issue we faced with PReview and PREP was the time commitment required for the Associate Provost running the program. Finding reviewers for some of the proposals was also difficult, but not insurmountable, likely due to the modest honorarium we offered. The major time commitment came from not only securing reviewers but the many 1:1 meetings and draft reviews. We often started with a solicitation and an idea and built up from there. This process trained faculty to be able to write successful proposals in the future without going through the program. While a similar program could be run in which proposals are simply sent out for review and the faculty receive the reviews, this approach would not be nearly as effective in the long run.

Aim 4. The primary challenge with this program was awareness and visibility. There was also lack of administrative support for developing and maintaining the website that featured the submitted scholarly works and highlight stories. In terms of tracking publications and scholarly works, we were not capturing all of the submissions each quarter because many faculty were unaware of the program, despite broad and continuous advertising.

FIGURE U2

Total dollar amounts of grants submitted and awarded at USD the two years before (2021-2023) and during (2023-2025) the described initiatives

In general our approach to culture shifting was focused on quality over quantity, trading mass advertisement and base level support services for close mentoring and high-quality interactions with faculty interested in taking advantage of new services.

Outcomes and Impact

One of the primary metrics of success is increased grant proposal submissions and success rate. However, it is important to consider that these systems change initiatives were pursued in a time when there were large scale cuts in external grant funding across nearly all federal agencies. With this climate in mind, we still saw significant gains in total dollar amounts of grant submitted and awarded in the two year period (Fig U2). The first year of the programs witnessed a 45% increase in dollars submitted and in the second year of the programs, USD was awarded over \$20M in grant dollars for the first time in its history.

FIGURE 3

Survey results from (A) faculty who attended workshops on (B) grant proposals and (C) grant budgets.

Survey responses were based on a 5-point likert scale. Nearly all responses were highly positive (>4).

C.

We also used participant surveys to gauge success of workshops which were overwhelmingly positive (Fig U3). The workshops also attracted faculty from all schools and disciplines (Fig U3A) Nearly all average responses were between 4 and 5 on a 5 point likert scale (Fig U3B,C), suggesting that the workshops were viewed as important and useful for a range of different fields. In response to how likely they are to recommend the workshop to their colleagues the response average was 4.6, indicating continued offering of the workshops will continue to reap benefits.

Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The cohesive approach is rooted in low cost and high-interaction programming designed to make meaningful connections and build relationships between faculty and R&D administrators and give faculty the agency and the sense of support to ensure their continued success in research. They are based on the old adage *'give a man a fish and he eats for a day, teach him to fish and he eats for lifetime.'* Hard work laying a foundation of intensive research support will elevate a small number of faculty to excel in grant writing and research success who can in turn help with programming and mentoring of other faculty.

Moreover, depending on your institutional resources and climate, any of these Aims and/or programs can be implemented independent of one another and can be scaled up or down or modified to meet the needs of the faculty and institution. Because this approach is focused a lot on relationship building and shifting culture and perception, it requires dedicated administrators who are committed and believe in the work to provide the personalized support necessary for genuine culture shifting. Without this, the programs will still provide additional resources for research development and

enhance the visibility of research support and recognition on campus but it may not have lasting impact if there is not faculty buy-in because do not trust that their voices are being heard and instead they sense that the administration is simply paying lip service to their desire for research to be more valued on campus without making lasting changes and culture shifts.

Sustainable research growth requires shifting from a top-down mandate to a stakeholder-centered mission. By rooting every new program in climate assessments and maintaining a 'long-game' mentality, we ensured that institutional investments in personnel and infrastructure translated into a shared mental model where faculty felt empowered to prioritize their scholarship.

University of Tennessee, Knoxville

Problem

UTK needed a clear, consistent, and equitable PI eligibility policy to support interdisciplinary research, enable faculty across appointment types to participate fully in externally funded projects, and strengthen the university's ability to compete for large-scale center and institute grants aligned with its AAU ambitions.

Goals and Success Criteria

For UTK, the primary conditions of the systems change were policies, practices, and mental models. The secondary conditions were resource flows, power dynamics, and relationships and connections. The motivating question for UTK was: "How can we increase the number of applications for multi-million dollar grants that support a center or institute for interdisciplinary research?"

As an R1 with the high research activity, complexity, and infrastructure, UTK was at a stage of refining structural changes that complement transformative changes to increase research activity, especially among colleges that are teaching intensive.

Specifically, the need arose from new initiatives to promote the creation of new centers and institutes that could compete strategically for large funding opportunities with multiple principal investigators who would contribute to UTK's application for an AAU status. The interdisciplinary nature of centers and institutes have required a new policy that standardizes practices across the colleges on campus and across the University of Tennessee System as a whole. Thus, while not an ERI, UTK was navigating a familiar experience for ERIs working to shift policy and make structural changes that adequately value interdisciplinary expertise and its contributions to the larger research goals. This remains an iterative process that cycles through all six conditions of systems change.

With growing interest among credentialed employees in positions with a 100% teaching loads, and in alignment with the University's initiatives for growing centers and institute applications, the research office of the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) provided a review of policies at UTK and at peer and aspirational institutions that could support an evidence-based revision or creation of a standard PI eligibility policy. It required and responded to all six conditions of the systems change process.

The goal of this policy review was to learn about the creation and implementation of successful PI eligibility policies at peer and aspirational institutions. The central aims included the following:

- + **Aim 1:** Determine which office wrote the policy or procedure for PI Eligibility status
- + **Aim 2:** Identify the distinction between those who have permanent PI Eligibility status and those who do not.
- + **Aim 3:** Clarify the process by which a faculty member can request temporary PI Eligibility status if they do not currently have it.
- + **Aim 4:** Review what research development offices require if a faculty member receives temporary PI Eligibility status.

These aims were then synthesized into a summary report with examples that decision-makers could use when reviewing the need to create or revise an eligibility policy.

Process and Implementation

RESOURCE FLOWS

As a point of departure, this case study began with initiatives at CAS with over 700 faculty to support new interdisciplinary centers and institutes. CAS was a uniquely positioned college to support interdisciplinary research for competitive applications to center and institute grants that draw from its 3 divisions of arts and humanities; natural sciences and mathematics; and social sciences. First, in response to calls for additional support for faculty, the Dean created the inaugural Office of Research and Creative Activity (ORCA) in 2023 to alleviate the burden of identifying and applying for external funding opportunities in light of increased demands on faculty time from teaching and service. One of the Office's first initiatives was to provide seed funding for dynamic working groups and new centers that would then apply for large, multi-million-dollar funding opportunities.

RELATIONSHIPS AND CONNECTIONS; POWER DYNAMICS

At several of the initial interest meetings, however, we noticed that the majority of the attendees had 100% teaching contracts with the institution and thus were not in positions that allowed them to apply as the lead primary investigators (PI) despite their equal credentials as experts in the respective emerging field of research. At that time, CAS did not have a PI Eligibility Policy to reference when determining who could and could not apply as a PI on a grant. Therefore, it would not be possible to determine equitably who could apply and receive credit for the allocated effort, even if the work would be done by a teaching-focused faculty or staff. It was also unclear who could make that determination and revealed varying practices over time towards this issue that would soon become immediately pressing if the College was to grow these centers and institutes.

MENTAL MODELS

This prompted a shift in thinking about who could be a PI on a grant application and what they would need in order to participate in research initiatives and external funding applications leveraging their expertise. This shift in mental models about who can be a PI matches larger hiring patterns in the United States such that now more than ever institutions have scholars in various positions who could be the lead PIs on competitive grants. Since 2010, the American Association of University Professors has raised the alarm of a shift in hiring practices and university compositions toward fixed-term positions and away from tenure track models (AAUP, 2010). The AAUP's 2023 update to the 2010 study shows that the number of non-tenure track and fixed-term faculty has increased from 30% in 1987 to over 50% in 2021, with tenure faculty declining to only 24% in that same time period (Colby, 2023). Recent budget constraints and resulting rescinded calls for faculty applications have accelerated this shift such that over 60% of faculty are now fixed-term hires with 100% teaching loads (Baker, 2025). Despite the fact that institutions now have scholars in various positions who could be the lead PIs

on competitive grants, aging research policies currently impede or exclude fixed-term hires from being PIs. This is a pressing concern as research development offices must shift their recruitment strategies to work with those already on campus during times of reduced budgets.

POLICIES

Specifically in the case of CAS, growing collaborative efforts into centers and institutes required applying to external funding opportunities, to which only a few team members could apply with their permanent PI status. Thus, in response to the interest of

Policy transformation begins with identifying the gaps between institutional rules and researcher realities. By shifting from ambiguous PI eligibility standards to a proactive, comparative review of peer-institution norms, we transitioned from an ad-hoc system of 'informal habits' to a coordinated framework that empowers all faculty—regardless of appointment type—to drive interdisciplinary innovation.

stakeholders in these emerging fields of research, we sought clarification on the PI eligibility policy for UTK. At the time, UTK's Office of Research, Innovation, and Economic Development (ORIED) defined PI eligibility on their external website. For 100% teaching faculty, it was unclear if they have eligibility as "Non-tenure Track Faculty who are paid UT employees" or if they have contingent eligibility depending on dean or chair approval as "Adjunct faculty" or "Lecturers." Some offices like the Global Catalyst Program further defined PI eligibility as a guarantee that the PI can execute the sponsored project solely at UTK beyond their current fixed-term contract. This required a letter from the department head indicating a long-term commitment to the PI for their ability to complete the sponsored project at UTK. While the University of Tennessee System did not define PI eligibility, it did have policies about research conduct that applied broadly to any paid or unpaid person engaged in research. Thus, whether or not the

faculty member had a 100% teaching load or not, they were held to the same standards.

PRACTICES

In the process of conducting the policy review for CAS, the unclear policy was not applied in the same way across colleges on campus, which impeded proposal development when applying for an interdisciplinary or team science collaborative grant. Some colleges had standardized practices to review PI eligibility requests, and others had informal habits that could assist a teaching-intensive faculty to acquire temporary PI status. CAS organized a meeting with all the relevant research development offices at UTK to compare our practices, and it was agreed that the different practices would

make it difficult to collaborate more regularly, especially for a large center and institute. Ultimately, having clear policies helps create equitable and accessible practices, and in case of an audit, a written procedure serves as back-up documentation for reasoning.

POLICIES AND PRACTICES

After reviewing the policies and practices at UTK, we provided an additional review of the published policies and practices of peer and aspirational institutions for a survey of norming practices in the field of research development and research administration. Specifically, this study surveyed thirteen R1 institutions, half of which are AAUs. Using a comparative methodology, we reviewed published policies and procedures that clarified PI eligibility status for external funding opportunities as well as faculty handbooks for further clarification on effort allocation. This survey found that most institutions have written or revised their policies and procedures within the past 4 years (2021-2024). The policy determines who has permanent PI Status and therefore does not need additional approval to apply for external funding opportunities. The procedure applies to those to whom the policy does not extend permanent PI status, because the procedure allows them to apply for temporary PI status. Overall, this study identified norming practices around PI eligibility policies that then determine who a research development office can support for external funding.

As a first step, we chose the peer and aspirational institutions based on UTK's Office of Budget and Finance and the Office of Institutional Research and Strategic Analysis. We also posted inquiries to the virtual boards of professional organizations like the National Council of University Research Administration and the National Organization of Research Development Professionals for examples from institutions with large teaching faculty since our main concern was how to incorporate faculty with 100% teaching loads into the research enterprise.

Once we defined the parameters and metrics for the policy review, we reviewed published policies and procedures that clarified PI Eligibility status for external funding opportunities. We also reviewed faculty handbooks for further clarification on effort allocation and what constituted 100% teaching loads. We then represented this information in the form of graphs that could be reviewed at a glance (Table 2). Additional information based on total research expenditures, public or private status, and an integrated medical center contextualized the choice of policy and practice

TABLE 2

Review of Policies and Practices for Determining PI Eligibility Status

Total Research Expenditures	Determining Factor for Permanent PI Status	Process for Temporary PI Status
\$904 million	Length of Contract	Reappointment Required
\$570.9 million	Percentage of Effort	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$704.1 million	Length of Contract	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$349.3 million	Length of Contract	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$231 million	Length of Contract	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$699 million	Length of Contract	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$1.7 billion	TT Status	RD/RA Office Request Form
\$633 million	TT Status	Department Initiated
\$1 billion	TT Status	Department Initiated
\$453.4 million	Length of Contract	Department Initiated

since these data indicate the kinds of resource flows at the respective institution. For the final report, we included the example policies and the corresponding definition of teaching loads from the faculty handbook for reference.

Table 2 reflects the policies and practices of peer and aspirational institutions as they relate to permanent and temporary PI Eligibility Status. The institutions are represented by their total research expenditures, and they are all public R1 institutions with a medical center. In each case, the determining factor for permanent PI eligibility was based on how the faculty handbook defined 100% teaching loads or research effort. Fixed-term employees have a defined pathway by which to request temporary PI status in all but one of the institutions, which would require a reappointment before receiving temporary PI status.

The review of PI Eligibility policies identified the following norming practices that were relevant to the central aims:

- + **Aim 1:** The central research office of the university or university system typically writes the policy or procedure for PI Eligibility status.
- + **Aim 2:** The primary determining factor for permanent PI status is time: if the PI has a guaranteed length of employment that covers the project period, then they can apply.
- + **Aim 3:** If someone's role is 100% dedicated already, that person cannot serve as a PI on a project unless their department, Faculty Affairs, dean, etc. provides an exception or if the person's role is changed to one that allows them to conduct research and to serve as a PI as part of their normal responsibilities.
- + **Aim 4:** Research offices note that fixed-term faculty typically know less about the process of grants—both pre and post award—and need more support than other applicants. Three research offices required those who requested PI status to also complete training on applying to external funders. This additional requirement could take the form of online courses, a scholarship agenda, or a team science application. Regardless of the method to request PI status, the research office implementing the policy must clearly explain it and make it accessible to potential PIs. This is typically done on a website and/or with a request form.

Challenges and Tradeoffs

The next step for this iterative process would be to refocus on stakeholders. First, we would return to the new center and institute meetings to review with the faculty, teaching faculty, and staff about their interest in applying for grants. Then, we would organize another meeting with other research offices on campus with a focused discussion on how these policies might work in the kinds of applications that those offices submit. At the same time, we would meet with department heads and business managers to review how the policies might impact their department management. For this meeting, we would prepare in advance examples of how the grants would need to be written to cover the teaching requirements of those with temporary PI status upon award. The tradeoff is that this iterative process could continue without end, so at some point, a decision has to be made that matches individual needs with organizational goals.

The ultimate tradeoff in systems change is between exhaustive consensus and decisive action. While iterative stakeholder engagement ensures that new policies—like those for PI eligibility—are relevant and trusted, the process can become an ‘endless loop’ that delays the very clarity and support that faculty need in the present to drive innovation.

Ultimately, writing a PI eligibility policy is the prerogative of the University’s central research office or central unit like a Faculty Senate or Provost Office. The PI Rights Policy of the University is the primary driver of the types of support that could be provided by a research development office. The most relevant policies represent faculty interests in addition to the larger goal. At the core, however, PI eligibility policies reflect the underlying culture, beliefs, and assumptions about who can and who cannot conduct research.

Thus, it would take a large organizing effort to write such a policy for CAS. In other words, to do so, the College would need to base its policy on a larger, University-wide policy and work to make sure that it did not contradict the larger one while also still making it relevant to the context of doing research

in the College. The report therefore generated more conversations rather than resulting in a refined policy that faculty with 100% teaching loads need now when deciding to participate in a center or institute or not. A policy review such as the one suggested only starts the conversation among decision-makers to write or review a policy, and they may decide not to do so.

Outcomes and Impact

The main outcome of this report was to generate ongoing conversations about the iterative process of writing policies and procedures that respond to stakeholder needs while meeting the institutional compliance and resource constraints, all of which are necessary for creating compliant, complete, and competitive grants that can be efficiently and successfully implemented upon award. Specifically, the report was shared at NORDP's annual meeting in 2025. It was also shared with 5 research offices at UTK. The central research office at UTK submitted this study with the TN System to use when writing a clearer PI Eligibility policy for the entire TN System of 5 universities. The new policy is expected in the coming year. This stronger research infrastructure will thereby support all potential PIs in the TN System in an ever-changing research landscape.

Lessons Learned and Recommendations

Policies emerge from stakeholder needs. Writing policies that work is an iterative process and requires collaboration across research offices at all levels in an institution, so first and foremost, be patient with the process and listen well to the interests of all when creating policies that also safeguard the institution's resources and constraints when conducting research. The guardrails are there for a reason, but if that reason has changed as in the case of changing hiring practices and research funding, then that takes careful consideration in light of the institution's new stage of emerging research.

When advocating for policy change, start with the stakeholders on campus: faculty members, staff, and research offices. Keep in mind the larger institutional goals, which were in UTK's case the application for AAU status and initiatives to increase center and institute grant applications. Where these interests align is the main focus of a review policy among peer and aspirational institutions. Discussions with professional associations like NCURA and NORDP are also key to identifying norming practices and standards of excellence in the field that respond to the current funding landscape. Then, synthesize this information into a digestible, one-page summary using graphs and tables when appropriate. While this study did not use quantitative data, it illustrates how you can translate qualitative information into a visual format. Lastly, find ways to present this information for peer review both internal to your institution and external to the profession for feedback on its application in real-world scenarios.

Summary of Lessons Learned

As evidenced by the three case studies, there is no single right way to approach developing and expanding RD and RSP activities. Despite substantial differences among the case study institutions, four key lessons and tools for success emerge.

1. **Climate Assessment:** Sustainable transformation requires a deep understanding of institutional context. In these case studies, stakeholder input was essential to gain this understanding. Hofstra relied on focus groups, surveys, and targeted listening sessions; USD used campus climate surveys and listening sessions; and UTK responded directly to feedback from stakeholders engaged in RD programming. In each case, subsequent actions aligned with the needs and perspectives expressed by these stakeholders.

Systems change is not a linear administrative task, but a relational 'long game.' By grounding every structural investment—from policy updates to new personnel—in authentic stakeholder climate assessments, institutions can bridge the gap between administrative ambition and faculty reality to build a resilient, shared culture of research excellence.

2. **Long-game Mentality:** RD investments are inherently long-term and require sustained commitment. This is particularly important for institutions experiencing turnover in RD/RSP personnel or in administrative roles that shape RD/RSP priorities. Institutionalizing processes and structures helps ensure continuity to the RD/RSP initiative to support stakeholders throughout their research process, which can take several years from ideation to an external funding proposal. Keeping this long-game mentality in mind, and continuing to emphasize this idea to stakeholders, will prevent fatigue: if initiatives wane after a year or two, then uncertainty of learning new processes again can discourage engagement. Make clear the timeline anticipated to see results for each initiative pursued and continue to be transparent with this timeline and expectations.

3. **Benchmarks:** Institutions should establish clear benchmarks for success, paired with realistic timelines for assessing progress, to allow RD investments to reach fruition. Formative checkpoints can support midcourse adjustments, but institutions must allow sufficient time for changes to take effect and produce measurable outcomes. Each institution should develop benchmarks appropriate for the movement they hope to see from their current to their desired state. This could include the number of professional development programs offered and level of engagement with those programs; number and size of proposals developed; and more qualitative benchmarks such as stakeholder satisfaction.

4. **Conceptual Anchors:** There are multiple entry points to RD development and RSP expansion. As ERIs and MSIs consider their goals with respect to RD/RSP, the six conditions of systems change can serve as a conceptual anchor to identify actionable strategies and understand how efforts across different conditions contribute to broader institutional transformation. Indeed, each case study institution emphasized a different condition while simultaneously addressing other conditions.

We offer the six conditions of systems change as a reflective and planning tool that helps institutions identify opportunities for action. The degree to which each condition is addressed will vary based on an institution's starting point, personnel, resources, culture, and goals. Engaging with the six conditions of systems change encourages institutions to work across structural, relational, and transformational levels of change, increasing the likelihood of sustained, meaningful institutional transformation.

Resources

A suite of open access modules (<https://www.stem2network.org/modules>), including a module on the six conditions of systems change, is available to help institutions apply the six conditions framework in their own contexts and to achieve their own goals.

The modules were developed by the (STEM)2 Network, a regional network of biology, chemistry, mathematics, and physics faculty advancing institutional transformation in support of STEM student success, with support from the National Science Foundation (Award Nos. 1919614, 2121495).

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